

Acta Medica Young Doctors

Original Article

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Accepted Date: 2025-09-02

Bibliyografi

Seasonal Distribution of Urticaria Patients: Mediterranean Region

ABSTRACT

Background: Urticaria, a common skin condition, is often influenced by various factors, including environmental conditions. While some studies suggest a link between urticaria and seasonal changes, the relationship is complex and can vary by geographical location and urticaria subtype. This study aimed to examine the relationship between urticaria and season-weather conditions in the Mediterranean region of Turkey.

Methods: This was a retrospective study conducted on patients diagnosed with urticaria who presented to the emergency department of a tertiary hospital in the Mediterranean region throughout 2023. Data were analyzed to assess the relationship between urticaria and categorical variables (seasons, months, weather conditions) using the Pearson's chi-square test, and continuous meteorological variables (temperature, dew point, humidity, wind speed, and pressure) using the independent samples t-test. The statistical significance level was set at $p < 0.05$.

Results: The analyses revealed no statistically significant association between the frequency of urticaria and either seasons, months, or weather conditions. Pearson's chi-square tests showed no significant relationship with season ($p = 0.999$) or month ($p = 0.998$). Similarly, the independent samples t-test results indicated no significant differences in mean meteorological conditions between the groups with and without urticaria (all $p > 0.05$).

Conclusion: The findings suggest that the occurrence of urticaria in this study's sample is not dependent on seasonal or daily meteorological factors. This

indicates that the etiology of urticaria in this population may be more related to chronic, internal factors rather than external environmental triggers. Future studies should include a broader range of potential triggers like air pollutants or specific allergens to further explore this relationship.

Keywords: Urticaria, Meteorological Factors, Seasons

Introduction

Urticaria, commonly known as hives, is a prevalent skin condition characterized by the sudden appearance of itchy wheals and sometimes angioedema [1]. It affects up to 20% of the population at some point in their lives and can be classified as either acute or chronic, with chronic urticaria further divided into spontaneous or inducible types [2]. The condition is primarily mediated by mast cells and histamine, but recent research has identified other inflammatory cells and cytokines as contributors. Studies have shown that acute urticaria (AU) in children exhibits seasonal variations. In a study conducted in southern Germany, AU was more prevalent in winter and had another peak in June, with the lowest incidence in summer [3]. This pattern was linked to respiratory infections, which were more common during these peak times, suggesting a viral etiology for AU in children [4]. This subtype of urticaria, which is triggered by heat or exercise, has been reported to occur predominantly in winter. Patients experienced symptoms when exposed to heat during the winter but not in summer, indicating that acclimatization to heat might influence the occurrence of symptoms [5]. A study on asthma patients found that episodes of acute urticaria were more frequent during seasonal exacerbations of asthma, suggesting a link between respiratory conditions and urticaria during certain seasons [6]. In this study, we aimed to examine the relationship between urticaria and season-weather conditions.

Materials and methods

This retrospective study was conducted on patients diagnosed with urticaria who visited the emergency department of a tertiary hospital serving the Mediterranean region during 2023. In the course of the research study, the collected data from the patients' medical records were subjected to rigorous analysis. Patients with urticaria were grouped according to season, month, and meteorological conditions, including temperature, dew point, humidity, wind speed, and pressure.

Weather data was obtained by creating an API based on data from the meteorological station serving the area where the hospital is located.

Statistical Analysis

The statistical analyses were conducted using the SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Sciences) for Windows 27.0 program. The data were subsequently classified. Categorical data were defined as percentages and frequencies. The numeric data were defined, and a distribution analysis was performed. Data following a normal distribution were defined as mean \pm standard deviation (SD). For data sets that did not adhere to a normal distribution, the median and interquartile range (IQR) were determined. The chi-square test was employed to ascertain the relationship between categorical data. The analysis of numeric tests that followed a normal distribution was conducted using parametric tests (t-tests). Statistical findings with a p-value below 0.05 were considered to be significant.

Result

The study revealed that patients suffering from urticaria sought treatment on 160 days of the year. When the data were examined in conjunction with the Pearson Chi-Square test results, no statistically significant relationship was identified between the seasons and the incidence of urticaria ($\chi^2(3, N = 365) = 0.024, p = 0.999$). The findings

of this study suggest that the onset of urticaria does not exhibit a specific seasonal pattern and demonstrates a uniform distribution throughout the year (see Table 1).

A Pearson's chi-square test was performed to examine the relationship between month and the presence of urticaria. The findings indicated an absence of a statistically significant association between the two variables, as evidenced by the result of the chi-squared test ($\chi^2(11, N = 365) = 2.094, p = 0.998$). The p-value of 0.998 is considerably higher than the conventional alpha level of 0.05, suggesting that the observed distribution of urticaria cases across the months is probably attributable to chance (see Table 2).

However, the statistical analysis revealed no evidence of a significant correlation between weather conditions and the occurrence of urticaria ($\chi^2(3, N = 365) = 1.358, p = 0.715$, Table 3). These findings suggest that meteorological factors do not have a statistically significant effect on the onset of urticaria. A meticulous examination of the meteorological conditions reveals no substantial disparities between the two groups (see Table 4).

Discussion

The relationship between urticaria and weather conditions is complex, involving various meteorological factors that can influence the frequency and severity of urticaria flare-ups [7]. Urticaria is characterised by itchy wheals and, in some cases, angioedema. Environmental conditions, including temperature, humidity and sunlight exposure, can trigger or exacerbate urticaria [8]. Studies have shown that these factors can significantly impact the frequency of emergency department visits and outpatient consultations related to urticaria. This article will explore the specific meteorological parameters associated with urticaria, drawing on recent research findings [9].

Higher temperatures have been linked to an increased risk of urticaria. For example, a study conducted in Turkey found that patients with urticaria were more likely to visit the emergency department during the summer months, when daily maximum and minimum temperatures were higher [10]. Similarly, research in China indicated that high temperatures increased the risk of outpatient visits for urticaria, with a notable cumulative effect observed over a 0–7 day lag period [11]. Relative humidity also plays a crucial role in urticaria incidence. In Turkey, for example, lower humidity levels were associated with a higher likelihood of urticaria presentations [12]. Increased exposure to sunlight has also been linked to a higher probability of urticaria. A Turkish study reported that each additional hour of sunshine increased the likelihood of urticaria by 7.4% [13]. This suggests that sunlight exposure may be a significant trigger for urticaria in susceptible individuals. The presence of air pollutants such as CO, NO₂ and O₃ has been shown to influence urticaria incidence. High concentrations of these pollutants have been associated with an increased risk of urticaria visits, with the effects persisting for several days [14]. This highlights the potential for air quality to exacerbate urticaria symptoms, particularly in urban environments. However, urticaria is a multifaceted condition influenced by various triggers, including allergens, stress, and underlying health conditions [15]. Chronic urticaria, in particular, may have autoimmune or idiopathic origins, which makes identifying specific environmental triggers difficult. The relationship between urticaria and seasonal patterns is complex and varies depending on the type of urticaria and the geographical location. For example, acute urticaria (AU) in children often exhibits seasonal trends, with peaks occurring in certain months, whereas cholinergic urticaria tends to be more prevalent in winter [16]. The seasonality of urticaria is influenced by environmental factors such as temperature and humidity, and is often associated with respiratory

infections, which are a common trigger. This overview will explore the seasonal patterns of urticaria, with a focus on acute and cholinergic urticaria, as well as the potential triggers associated with these patterns [17]. One study conducted in London found that most acute urticaria cases in children occurred in autumn, with a significant peak in November. This suggests a seasonal trend potentially linked to environmental changes or increased respiratory infections during this time [18]

In southern Germany, acute urticaria in children showed a higher incidence in winter and another peak in June. This pattern was independent of sex and was not observed in children under five years old. These peaks coincided with increased respiratory infections, suggesting a potential link between viral infections and urticaria [19]. Cholinergic urticaria, which is characterised by small, itchy welts triggered by heat or exercise, was found to predominantly occur in winter. Patients experienced symptoms when exposed to heat or exercise during this period, but not during the summer months. This suggests that acclimatisation to heat may play a role in the manifestation of symptoms [20].

Across various studies, respiratory infections were identified as a common trigger for acute urticaria. These infections are more prevalent in the colder months, which may explain the seasonal peaks in urticaria cases [21]. There is a noted association between asthma exacerbations and episodes of acute urticaria, particularly during seasonal changes. This relationship highlights the role of mast cell activation and histamine release in both conditions [22].

The analyses conducted by season and month reveal one of the most salient findings of this study. The application of both seasonal (spring, summer, fall, winter) and monthly chi-squared tests revealed no statistically significant relationship between the incidence of urticaria and time (month or season) ($p > 0.05$). These results support the

hypothesis that urticaria is not specific to a particular season or month in the population studied, but occurs at similar rates throughout the year. Contrary to the prevailing assumption that urticaria is directly related to pollen or other seasonal allergens, this finding suggests that the etiology of urticaria in the sample studied may be linked to other factors, such as chronic causes, medications, or foods. Subsequent studies may encompass diverse populations and environmental factors from disparate regions to substantiate this finding and investigate the underlying causes of urticaria with greater depth.

The findings of this study provide important insights into the relationship between the onset of urticaria and environmental factors. The analyses indicated that there was no statistically significant effect on the incidence of urticaria in terms of both seasonal and monthly distributions and various meteorological variables (temperature, humidity, wind speed, etc.).

Preliminary cross-tabulation analyses indicated that urticaria cases exhibited minimal variation across different months and seasons of the year, with incidence rates maintaining a relatively stable trend. This finding was statistically confirmed by Pearson Chi-Square test results ($p > 0.05$). In addition, the independent samples t-test results indicated that there was no statistically significant difference in the average meteorological conditions experienced by individuals with and without urticaria ($p > 0.05$).

The findings of this study suggest that the hypothesis linking urticaria to environmental triggers is not supported by the data. The analysis indicates that external environmental conditions, such as season, month, and weather, do not appear to be significant factors in the sample under study. This observation indicates that the etiology of urticaria cases may be more associated with chronic causes, food allergies, drug reactions, or other internal factors.

Future studies should utilize larger samples from diverse geographic regions to examine the environmental relationship of urticaria in greater depth. These studies should also analyze more specific variables, such as pollen counts, air pollution levels, and other environmental chemicals. The findings of this study offer significant insights into the understanding of urticaria, suggesting that individual and internal factors may exert a more substantial influence than general weather conditions.

Limitation

The present study is not without its limitations, which may have ramifications for the generalizability of its findings. Firstly, the study employs a retrospective design and is exclusively based on data from patients who visited the emergency department of a single hospital in the Mediterranean Region throughout 2023. This may limit the generalizability of the results to patients with urticaria in other geographical regions or larger populations. Secondly, the present study exclusively examined the relationship between general meteorological conditions (season, month, temperature, humidity, wind, and pressure) and the incidence of urticaria. The analyses indicated that these external environmental conditions are not the sole determining factors. However, the study's limitations precluded the investigation of more specific factors that may contribute to the etiology of urticaria, including the pollen count, levels of air pollution, stress levels, food allergies, drug reactions, and underlying chronic

causes. Consequently, subsequent studies should incorporate these variables to more thoroughly examine the environmental aspects of urticaria.

Conclusion

The present study examined data from patients who visited the emergency department with a diagnosis of urticaria in the Mediterranean Region in 2023. The analyses indicated that there was no statistically significant relationship between the incidence of urticaria and the seasons, months, and various meteorological variables (temperature, dew point, humidity, wind speed, and pressure).

Despite the existence of prior research indicating seasonal fluctuations, particularly with regard to specific subtypes, such as acute urticaria and cholinergic urticaria in children, the results of the present study offer a divergent perspective. The data obtained demonstrate that urticaria cases in the sample under study exhibited a relatively stable distribution throughout the year, indicating that external environmental factors alone are not the determining triggers (3333).

This observation indicates that the etiology of urticaria in patients may be more associated with chronic causes, food allergies, or internal factors such as drug reactions. Consequently, this study provides a valuable perspective that individual and internal factors may play a more important role in understanding urticaria than general weather conditions.

Season	<i>No Urticaria</i>		<i>Urticaria Yes</i>		<i>Total</i>	
	<i>n</i>	<i>%</i>	<i>n</i>	<i>%</i>	<i>n</i>	<i>%</i>
<i>Spring</i>	50	24.4%	40	25.0%	90	24.7%
<i>Summer</i>	52	25.4%	40	25.0%	92	25.2%
<i>Autumn</i>	52	25.4%	40	25.0%	92	25.2%
<i>Winter</i>	51	24.9%	40	25.0%	91	24.9%
<i>Total</i>	205	100.0%	160	100.0%	365	100.0%

Table 1. Urticaria patients seasonal comperation

Month	No Urticaria		Urticaria Yes	
	n	%	n	%
1	18	8.8%	13	8.1%
2	16	7.8%	12	7.5%
3	16	7.8%	15	9.4%
4	19	9.3%	11	6.9%
5	17	8.3%	14	8.8%
6	15	7.3%	15	9.4%
7	19	9.3%	12	7.5%
8	18	8.8%	13	8.1%
9	17	8.3%	13	8.1%
10	17	8.3%	14	8.8%
11	17	8.3%	13	8.1%
12	16	7.8%	15	9.4%
Total	205	100.0%	160	100.0%

Table 2. Urticaria patients monthy comperation

Weather Condition	No Urticaria		Urticaria Yes		Total	
	n	%	n	%	n	%
Fair	99	48.3%	84	52.5%	183	50.1%
Windy	8	3.9%	6	3.8%	14	3.8%
Rainy	11	5.4%	11	6.9%	22	6.0%
Cloudy	87	42.4%	59	36.9%	146	40.0%
Total	205	100.0%	160	100.0%	365	100.0%

Table 3. Urticaria patients wather condition comperation

Variable	No Urticaria (n=205)		Urticaria Yes (n=160)		t	df	p
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD			
Temperature	22.20	7.98	22.13	7.96	76	363	939
Dew Point	11.13	7.41	11.09	7.58	42	363	967
Humidity (%)	54.06	20.94	54.47	22.06	-179	363	858
Wind Speed (km/h)	13.75	8.13	13.17	7.74	694	363	488
Pressure (hPa)	1007.02	6.12	1007.62	5.78	-954	363	341

Table 4. Urticaria patients wather comperation

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